

Synthesis and Characterisation of certain Polycitraconimides and Biscitraconimides

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Citraconic anhydride has been reacted with several amines and diamines to obtain a novel class of high temperature resistant citraconimides and biscitraconimides. Initially citraconamic acids have been separated and characterised. The intermediate amic acids are imidized and the imidization is carefully followed. The imides and bisimide monomers have been polymerized by thermal process in nitrogen atmosphere. Thermal polymerization of the monomers has been investigated by differential scanning calorimetry. Thermal decomposition has been investigated by TGA.

Bismaleimides are low molecular weight prepolymers, endcapped with reactive maleimide rings. These are polymerizable thermally or by a Michael-type reaction into highly crosslinked and heat-resistant polyimides without the elimination of by-products¹. Polymethylene bismaleimides, poly-*p,p'*-bismaleimidodiphenylmethane and low melting ternary bismaleimide mixtures are described in literature². The high temperature stabilities may be influenced by the incorporation of aromatic or heterocyclic rings in the backbone.

N-Alkylene biscitraconimides³ were synthesised from the corresponding *N*-alkylene biscitraconamic acids or directly from citraconic anhydride and a homologous series of aliphatic diamines. The intermediate biscitraconamic acids or biscitraconimides were polymerized thermally at 175–225° to tough amber coloured film of polybiscitraconimides that exhibited good thermal stability. Though aromatic polyimides have met the requirements of high temperature environments to a considerable extent, investigations have been carried out to develop a new concept of chain extension and curing high temperature resistant polymers in the forms of polyimides via the addition polymerization process⁴. The need for such a process was apparent since polyimides produced by condensation reactions liberate large quantities of volatile byproducts during polymerization and curing. On the other hand low molecular weight addition polyimides based on short, preimidized segments, however, polymerize thermally through end-groups without the loss of volatile byproducts. With that idea behind, we have synthesised several citraconimides and biscitraconimide monomers via the formation of the intermediate citraconamic and biscitraconamic acids and then to the corresponding polymers (Schemes 1 and 2).

Scheme 1. Preparation of citraconimides and polycitraconimides.

Scheme 2. Preparation of biscitraconimides and polycitraconimides

Results and Discussion

The physical data of the monomers and polymers are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Electronic spectra of the citraconimide and biscitraconimide monomers show an intense peak at 240 ± 20 nm indicating the presence of double bond in the anhydride moiety. An additional band observed at 265 ± 15 nm is due to the presence of aromatic rings except in N_3 derived from azodiamine, which shows a band at 455 nm associated with transition in the azo group.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF CITRACONIMIDES (M) AND BISCITRACONIMIDES (N)*

Monomer code	Monomer	Colour	M.p.** °C	Yield %
M ₁	Citraconimide of 2-aminoacetophenone	Yellow	163 ^a	80
M ₂	Citraconimide of 4-aminothiol	Brown	172 ^b	75
M ₃	Citraconimide of 2-aminothiol	Yellow	129 ^b	85
M ₄	Citraconimide of 1-naphthylamine	Orange	136 ^a	70
M ₅	Citraconimide of β-aminoazobenzene	Orange	138 ^c	90
N ₁	Biscitraconimide of 2-nitro-1,4-phenylenediamine	Yellow	153 ^a	80
N ₂	Biscitraconimide of 2,4-diaminotoluene	Brown	110 ^b	80
N ₃	Biscitraconimide of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone	Orange	227 ^a	85
N ₄	Biscitraconimide of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone	White	175 ^a	90
N ₅	Biscitraconimide of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylether	White	184 ^a	85
N ₆	Biscitraconimide of 1,12-diaminododecane	Creamish	68 ^b	60

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Solvent of crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bpetrol, ^cC₆H₆.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF POLYMERS

Polymer code ^a	Time (h)/ °C	Colour	η dl g ⁻¹
PM ₁	3/240, 1/290	Brown	0.095
PM ₂	3/220, 1/270	Dark brown	0.13
PM ₃	3/175, 1/225	Brown	0.12
PM ₄	3/190, 1/240	Amber	0.10
PM ₅	3/190, 1/240	Orange	0.12
PN ₁	3/210, 1/260	Amber	0.32
PN ₂	3/160, 1/210	Amber	0.23
PN ₃	3/270, 1/320	Reddish	0.25
PN ₄	3/225, 1/275	Amber	0.24
PN ₅	3/235, 1/285	Pink	0.29
PN ₆	3/120, 1/170	Pale brown	0.21

^aCorresponding polymer (P) of monomer (M/N) in Table 1.

Ir spectra of the intermediates as amic acids and bisamic acids show characteristic bands at 3 270, 1 560 and 1 770 cm⁻¹. These bands disappeared after imidization and new bands appeared at 1 785, 1 720, 1 390 and 690 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the imide structure. A very strong ring stretching band appears at 1 150 cm⁻¹ for citraconimides as well as biscitraconimides confirming the presence of C–N–C linkage. In addition to the strong C=O absorption, C=C stretching vibrations show weak band at 1 610 cm⁻¹. All the monomers show a peak at 2 900 cm⁻¹ for CH₃ group of

citraconimide or biscitraconimide. All the citraconimides and biscitraconimides show multiple bands at 800–1 200 cm⁻¹ assigned to the in-plane and out-of-plane bending vibrations of the C–H bands characteristic of the aromatic systems. Considering the ir data of the monomers and polymers it is found that the bands due to ethylenic double bond of all monomers appearing around 1 640 and 840 cm⁻¹ disappeared on polymerization. In all the polymers new bands appear at 2 930–2 980 cm⁻¹ (C–C–H). It is therefore concluded that polymerization proceeds by the ring-opening of the imide rings of the monomers.

¹H nmr spectra of the citraconamic acid and biscitraconamic acids show hydroxyl proton around δ 11 (1H, s, COOH) and NH protons at δ 7.6–7.8 (1H, s, NH). Spectra of the citraconamic acids, citraconamide and biscitraconamide show olefinic proton at δ 6.8–7.2 (1H, s, vinyl), CH₃ proton of citraconic moiety at δ 2.1–2.2 (3H, s, CH₃). In the bisimide of alkylene diamine (N₆), NCH₂ protons appear at δ 3.5 (4H, m, N–CH₂) and methylene protons at δ 1.6 (20H, m, CH₂). From the nmr data of polymers in DMSO-d₆ and comparing those with the data of the monomers, it is observed that the peak (δ 6.8–6.9) due to vinylic proton disappears in the spectra of the polymers and the shift due to CH₃ proton of the citraconyl moiety goes downfield from δ 2.2 to 1.6 or 1.8. These suggest that polymerization takes place with the opening up of the ethylenic double bond of the imide ring.

Thermogravimetric studies were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere for polybiscitraconimides at a heating rate 20°/min. The small weight-loss observed around 100–200° may be attributed to the expulsion of absorbed moisture. TG analysis carried out in air for polybiscitraconimides shows that they are fairly stable in air though oxygen atmosphere is generally known to favour degradation. A comparison of the TGA data reveals that polycitraconimides are relatively much stable than polybiscitraconimides. Almost 10% loss in weight was observed for most of the polymers around 300°. However, for PN₄ and PN₅ this was observed above 450° indicating that these two polymers had the maximum stability.

Differential thermal analyses in air were carried out for the polycitraconimides and polybiscitraconimides at a heating rate of 20°/min. The data reveal an endotherm in the region 150–200° from which glass transition temperatures (T_g) for the polymers were recorded. An exotherm was observed around 450–500° for most of the polymers while a second one was observed for PN₆ around 600°. The exotherms are due to the thermal oxidation reactions. The exotherm observed at 450° for PN₃ may be due to expulsion of nitrogen from the azo links. DSC data for the compounds were recorded in nitrogen atmosphere. Exothermic peaks were obtained in the temperature range 220–350°. These exotherms are presumably due to thermally induced polymerization reactions. DSC curves (Fig. 1) reveal that if curing is carried out at higher temperature (above 350°), degradation reactions may become important because in

most of the samples DSC results show the existence of the second exotherm above 400°.

Fig. 1. DSC thermograms of polymers.

The data (Table 3) show that the thermal degradation for these polymers occurs at high temperature. It is established that citraconic bisimide polymers are less stable than maleic bisimide polymers due to the presence of electron-donating methyl groups.

TABLE 3—THERMAL STABILITY DATA OF POLYMERS* FROM TGA

Polymer	IDT ^a (°C)	PDT ^b (°C)	PDT ^c (°C)	Y _c (%)
PM ₁	256	359	505	40
PM ₂	254	362	465	35
PM ₃	263	360	550	46
PM ₄	228	330	515	39
PM ₅	225	358	495	43
PN ₁	359	470	605	52
PN ₂	361	440	665	55
PN ₃	357	430	595	65
PN ₄	418	535	690	60
PN ₅	429	565	715	62
PN ₆	365	472	620	49

*Corresponds to polymers in Table 2.

^aInitial decomposition temperature. ^bPolymer decomposition temperature.

^cMaximum polymer decomposition temperature. ^dChar yield at 800°.

Experimental

Citraconic anhydride (Fluka) was vacuum-distilled. 2-Aminoacetophenone (Fluka), 2-aminothiol (Sigma), 4-aminothiol (Sigma), 1-naphthylamine (B.D.H.), β-aminoazobenzene (B.D.H.), 2-nitro-1,4-phenylenediamine

(Fluka) and 1,12-diaminododecane (Fluka) were used as received. 4,4'-Diaminoazobenzene, 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone and 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether were purified by crystallisation from alcohol.

The imide and bisimide monomers of citraconic anhydride were prepared by the cyclodehydration of the citraconamic and biscitraconamic acid precursor with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate using a slightly modified procedure described by Searle⁷. To a vigorously stirred solution of the diamine (0.1 mol) or amine (0.1 mol) in acetone under nitrogen, citraconic anhydride (0.22 mol) or citraconic anhydride (0.11 mol) respectively was added at room temperature over a period of 10 min. The yellowish solid of amic acid or bisamide acid was obtained. Excess solvent was then removed to isolate the amic or bisamic acid which was dried overnight at 60°. The acid value of the amic acid was determined. The rest of the acid was vigorously stirred with DMF (100 ml) for 1 h to get a clear solution. Acetic anhydride (14.2 ml) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g) were added to it with stirring and refluxed for 3 h at 40° until the solution became clear. The brown or brownish yellow solution was then poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried in air and kept in vacuum desiccator for 2–3 days.

Polymers were prepared by thermal polymerization via the polyaddition technique. A known weight of the monomer was heated in nitrogen atmosphere for 30 min in a glass tube. The temperature was raised by 50° above the melting point and maintained at that temperature for 3 h. Again temperature was raised to 50° and kept at that temperature for another 1 h. The resulting polymers were washed with DMF and acetone and dried under reduced pressure (yields 60–90%).

Elemental analysis of the monomers was carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 240B instrument. Electronic spectra (conc. H₂SO₄) were recorded on a Shimadzu 240 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO/CDCl₃) on a EM 390 spectrometer (90 MHz). TGA and DTA studies were done on a Shimadzu DT 30B instrument. Inherent viscosity was measured at 30 ± 0.1° in sulphuric acid (0.5% solution) using an Ubbelohde viscometer.

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